

NOTES

Synthesis and Characterisation of Halides and Complex Halogeno Anions as Salts of Bis(cyclopentadienyl)zirconium(IV) Chelates formed with 2,3-Dihydroxypyridine and 2-Amino-3-hydroxypyridine

SHASHI K. BANSAL, SHIELLA TIKKU and R. S. SINDHU*
Chemistry Department, Regional College of Education,
Ajmer-305 004

and

YOGENDRA SINGH

Chemistry Department, University of Delhi,
Delhi-110 007

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revised 16 September 1991, accepted 20 September 1991*

BIS(cyclopentadienyl)zirconium(IV) dichloride ($\text{Cp}_2\text{-ZrCl}_2$), an important precursor for a wide range of derivatives, can form chelates with uninegative bidentate ligands¹ in solution when the ratio of the M:L is 1:1. To extend the studies in this field we have tried the reaction of the uninegative bidentate ligands 2,3-dihydroxypyridine (DHP) and 2-amino-3-hydroxypyridine (AHP) with Cp_2ZrCl_2 in aqueous medium, and the complex species so formed were further treated with KI, KBr, NaClO_4 , ZnCl_2 , CdCl_2 , HgCl_2 and FeCl_3 salts resulting in the formation of insoluble salts. These insoluble salts have been characterised by elemental analysis, conductance, ir and pmr spectral studies.

Experimental

All the chemicals and reagents used were of AnalaR grade. Cp_2ZrCl_2 (Fluka) DHP and AHP (both Aldrich) were used.

Analyses for C and H were performed in Micro-analytical Laboratory of the Department of Chemistry, Delhi University. Nitrogen, halogen and metal contents were estimated by standard methods². Conductance measurements were made in nitrobenzene with a Toshniwal conductivity bridge at room temperature.

Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$ at a sweep width of 60 M Hertz and a sweep time of 300 seconds on a Hitachi Perkin-Elmer R-600 spectrometer using TMS as an internal reference.

Preparation of compounds: To an aqueous solution (50 ml) of Cp_2ZrCl_2 (5 mmol), DHP/AHP (5 mmol) was added and the mixture was stirred for 2 h. It was then added dropwise with shaking to a

concentrated hot aqueous solution containing an excess (6 mmol) of KI, KBr, NaClO_4 , ZnCl_2 , CdCl_2 , HgCl_2 and FeCl_3 , until no more precipitate was formed. It was then digested over a water-bath (60–70°) for 2 h, filtered, the solid washed with hot water and dried in vacuum over P_4O_{10} .

Results and Discussion

On the basis of elemental analysis the complexes of DHP and AHP have been assigned the compositions given in Table 1. The compositions have been further confirmed by conductance values (27.3–30.6 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) for all complexes except for $[(\text{Cp})_2\text{ZrL}]_2 \cdot \text{CdCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (56.6 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$). The complexes are thermally stable and decomposed at higher temperature without melting. They are moderately soluble in nitrobenzene, methanol and deuterated acetone.

The infrared spectra of the compounds show usual peaks for $\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5$ group³, viz. C–H stretching frequency at ~ 3085 , C–C asymmetric ring breathing mode of π -bond at ~ 1430 , C–H in-plane vibrations at ~ 1035 and C–H bending out-of-plane deformation at $\sim 815 \text{cm}^{-1}$. Apart from this, an additional band near 440cm^{-1} can be assigned to Zr–C₅H₅ vibration⁴.

A broad band of free DHP ligand at 3200cm^{-1} indicates hydrogen bonding (O–H...O)⁵, which disappeared in all the metal complexes showing simultaneous deprotonation and formation of M–O bond at 3-position. A strong band at 1625cm^{-1} (C=O) shifted to lower side in the complexes, which suggests that the ligand coordinates to metal through oxygen of carbonyl group at 2-position. Metal-to-oxygen bonding is further confirmed due to the presence of a band at $490\text{--}540 \text{cm}^{-1}$ (Zr–O)⁶. A relatively weak band at 3400cm^{-1} observed in free DHP and attributed to ν_{NH} of α -pyridone-like structure of DHP, remained unchanged in the complexes, suggesting its non-involvement in coordination.

In the ir spectra of free AHP, three bands at 3425 , 3375 and 3125cm^{-1} are assigned to ν_{OH} (O–H...N), ν_{NH} asymmetric and ν_{NH} symmetric vibrations respectively. Stretching O–H bands of the ligand disappeared in all the compounds showing simultaneous deprotonation and formation of M–O bond to take place at 3-position of the ligand. The ν_{NH} symmetric band at 3125cm^{-1} shifted to lower side by $30\text{--}40 \text{cm}^{-1}$, which indicates that nitrogen of amino group at 2-position is coordinated to metal atom in all the AHP complexes. The band at $470\text{--}500 \text{cm}^{-1}$ (Zr–N) further confirms the presence of a Zr–N bond⁷.

TABLE I—CHEMICAL SHIFT (δ) OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	C_5H_5	Protons of complex (HL=DHP)			
$[(Cp)_2ZrL]^+I^-$	6.64	1.72	1.80	2.60	1.84
$[(Cp)_2ZrL]^+Br^-$	6.62	1.72	1.80	2.60	1.84
$[(Cp)_2ZrL]^+ClO_4^-$	6.64	1.74	1.80	2.60	1.82
$[(Cp)_2ZrL]^+ZnCl_2^-$	6.62	1.74	1.80	2.60	1.82
$[(Cp)_2ZrL]^+CdCl_2^-$	6.58	1.74	1.80	2.60	1.84
$[(Cp)_2ZrL]^+HgCl_2^-$	6.64	1.72	1.80	2.60	1.82
$[(Cp)_2ZrL]^+FeCl_4^-$	6.64	1.74	1.80	2.60	1.82
Protons of complex (HL=AHP)					
		Protons of pyridine ring		Amine protons	
$[(Cp)_2ZrL]^+I^-$	6.64	3.2	1.82	2.72	7.30
$[(Cp)_2ZrL]^+Br^-$	6.62	3.2	1.82	2.74	7.32
$[(Cp)_2ZrL]^+ClO_4^-$	6.64	3.4	1.80	2.74	7.32
$[(Cp)_2ZrL]^+ZnCl_2^-$	6.64	3.4	1.82	2.70	7.30
$[(Cp)_2ZrL]^+CdCl_2^-$	6.58	3.2	1.80	2.72	7.32
$[(Cp)_2ZrL]^+HgCl_2^-$	6.62	3.4	1.80	2.70	7.32
$[(Cp)_2ZrL]^+FeCl_4^-$	6.60	3.4	1.80	2.72	7.32

*HL=DHP/AHP.

No halide bridging is observed in case of halide and complexohalogeno salts of $[(Cp)_2ZrL]$ chelates, where HL=DHP/AHP. The band at $360-390\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for the complex halo-anion salts are characteristics of complex haloanions⁸.

Pmr spectra of the complexes are recorded in Table I. The resonance signal due to C_5H_5 group occurs at $\sim\delta$ 6.60 ppm. The existence of single sharp C_5H_5 resonance is attributed to rapid rotation of ring about metal-ring axis⁹. In case of DHP and AHP complexes the values of chemical shifts of protons of chelated DHP and AHP indicate that there is bonding of zirconium through oxygen and oxygen atoms and oxygen and nitrogen atoms of the ligands respectively. The intensities of all the resonance lines were determined by planimetric integration. The integrated proton ratios correspond to the formula assigned to these compounds.

From the above studies it can be concluded that the ligand DHP or AHP is chelates with $(Cp)_2Zr^{2+}$ having a wedge-like sandwich structure with essentially tetrahedral coordination about the metal atom similar to that of dichloride¹⁰ and halides and complexohalogenoanions forming salts with the $[(Cp)_2ZrL]^+$ complex cationic species.

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